

>>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=a3Pfe2MP9_w

UPDATE on Strong Letter Response to Mr. Ben Davidson

Like the author said, Ben is FLAT WRONG

Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM
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Re: The Micronova and Moving Through the Galactic Sheet

From the Desk of Sf. Ramon Careaga, founder EPEMC, www.epemcgateway.com

Dear Readers,

In the first STRONG LETTER¹, dated Sep. 21, 2021, the author made this table about Ben's "predictions":

Table 1²

Flare	Date	Distance (AU)	Rel. Velocity		Prediction Date
Neptune	8/15/2020	10.9	0.04801762115		
Uranus	3/30/2021	9.6	0.05748502994	19.72%	
Saturn		4.4			10/15/2021
Jupiter	9/13/2021	3.7			1/15/2022
Mars	11/5/2021	0.5			4/2/2022
Earth	11/12/2021				4/13/2022

¹

https://www.academia.edu/53139271/Strong_Letter_Response_to_Mr_Ben_Davidson_Suspicious_Observers_et_al

² Credit: author,

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1dqVRar0VZed5TrMBdEmmIYA1v8ax-MPOX8VlpzAZdoQ/edit?usp=sharing>

It is best to give a brief update, given he has retained his assurances on the magnetic pole flip and micronova, etc., to describe his credibility in predictive (mimsical) scientific progress. Notably, as one other PEMster has observed, he has stopped trying to predict the galactic current sheet to arrive “at any moment.”

Er, so far, none of these bodies have flared in the manner predicted, and **certainly not on or around those dates**. There was a “devastating” impact on Jupiter on October 15, 2021³, and Jupiter has a well-known 40-year mystery of x-ray flaring⁴, that was solved⁵ in July of 2021. But to the author’s non-surprise, there was no flare event.

As for events in April of 2022, there was a cluster of X class flares⁶ on April 20, 2022 and this was “hurled towards Earth”⁷ but it didn’t come from a galactic current sheet, but from the sun. If that was the major prediction event, then it was quite disappointing at X2.

This does not *completely* eliminate Davidson’s credibility, however, it continues to expose his interest in grifting off of fear, more than exposing the science.

There is one area he has made progress in: which is correctly pointing out that NASA/NOAA still has not responded to his previous calls to include all predictive factors in climate change models⁸, and they, of course, have no incentive to do this in the current political environment. However, I suspect he knows this and is being a bit cheeky in expecting them to admit it or even do it, knowing they cannot in this environment. Maybe he can use all that money from the ‘ranch’ and pay to create the models. Either way, he should be more careful with his predictions, in the future (and don’t dox scientists!)

Cheerfully,
Sf. R. Careaga

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<https://universemagazine.com/en/the-fall-of-an-asteroid-on-jupiter-caused-an-explosion-by-the-force-of-a-nuclear-bomb/>

⁴ <https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/news/40-year-mystery-solved-source-of-jupiters-x-ray-flares-uncovered>

⁵ <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/sciadv.abf0851>

⁶ <https://www.swpc.noaa.gov/news/x2-flare-r3-strong-radio-blackout-20-april-2022-utc-day>

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<https://watchers.news/2022/04/20/major-x2-2-solar-flare-erupts-just-beyond-the-southwest-limb-of-the-sun/>

⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9Fx11vmgck0&t=0s>